

NODES

Nord Ovest Digitale E Sostenibile

NODES – Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile

ACCESSIBILITY TO THE BASIC SERVICES: preliminary analysis for the pilot area definition

SPOKE 4 – Montagna Digitale e Sostenibile

DELIVERABLE D3.1 INTERFACE

RESEARCH MODULE 3 - *Proof of Concept for a shared and collective transport service for rural communities*

Version history

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Glossary

	Definition
Hub Coordinator (HC)	The Hub Coordinator represents the single point of contact for the implementation of the innovation ecosystem towards the MUR. It carries out the management and coordination activities of the innovation ecosystem, receives the fundings, verifies, and transmits to the MUR the reporting of the activities carried out by the Spoke and their affiliates.
National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP)	This document uses the Italian acronym for the NRRP, which is PNRR (Piano Nazionale della Ripresa e Resilienza)
Research Program Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the NODES project. The NODES will appoint the Research Program Manager. It refers to “Responsabile del Programma di Ricerca” in the MUR’s Call of proposal for “Ecosistemi di Innovazione”
NODES’ Research and innovation program	NODES’ Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spoke, with the aim to promote and support applied research on topics consistent with the Intelligent Specialization Strategy, with the guidelines of the 2021-2027 partnership agreement scheme, with regional operational plans and regional and national research and innovation priorities. Although NODES’ Spokes are concentrated on different themes, they will organize their activities and actions within a common framework – NODES’ Booster Methodology
Spoke Coordinator	The University in charge of coordinating the Spoke’s ecosystem. It refers to “Spoke” in the MUR’s Call of proposal for “Ecosistemi di Innovazione”
Spoke Data Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the monitoring and management of data generated at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Data Manager.
Spoke Partner	The entity associated to the Spoke Coordinator. It can be an Innovation Cluster, Competence Center, Research Center related to the Spoke’s ecosystem and contributes to achieve objectives and impact under the Spoke’ leadership and management. It refers to “soggetti affiliati” in the MUR’s Call of proposal for “Ecosistemi di Innovazione”.
Spoke Project manager	The person who will be the responsible for the management, coordination and progress of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Project Manager.
Spoke research and innovation program	NODES’ Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spokes. The spoke will leverage a consolidated collaboration with leading private and public companies and will focus the applied research activity on technological domains and applications that can favour the integration of SMEs into new value chains.
Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager.
Spoke Stakeholders Committee (SC)	Consultation structure formed by relevant stakeholders (Government, universities, companies, civil society, third sector, etc.)
Spoke Thematic	General target focus and domain of the Spoke research.
Spoke Topics	Specific areas/lines of development within the Spoke.
Spoke Work Package Leader	At the Spoke level, Work Packages (WPs) will be organized by WP leaders, who will be responsible for performance evaluation and reporting.
Flagship Project	Main research project at the Spoke level with the goal of prototyping, testing, demonstrating the research activities towards higher TRLs.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report presents the analysis that has been carried out in the Val d'Aosta region in order to select the most significant pilot areas for the proposition of adaptive mobility services as part of the RM3 work program. A description of the demographic and socio-economic conditions is presented, complemented by the identification and mapping of the basic services (social, health, educational) for the area. A cluster analysis has then been performed and is here presented, which guided the selection of 2 pilot Units for the further quantification of the relative demand basin in numerical and geographical terms, presented in D3.2.

The present report provides a clear picture of the accessibility to main attraction poles, with indications about level of service, needed integration of service availability and mobility needs.

Besides investigating current mobility needs, the last section considers that many services, especially following the pandemic, have been digitized and do not require moving, as well as the home-work trips decreased thanks to the strengthening of smart working practices: in particular, a focus is provided on the availability of digital services for the health sector.

A) Analysis of the basic services accessibility in mountainous areas

This section is articulated as follows:

- A recognition of the literature to identify and select the basic services and accessibility models specifically in mountain areas;
- Definition of the context and illustration of the cluster analysis methodology;
- Mapping and clustering according to the basic services typology;
- A clustering according to the mobility generators, mobility demand and vulnerability.
- A recognition of solutions and strategies for the digitalization of health services.

Basic services in mountainous areas and their accessibility

Fair access to basic services is a fundamental topic of public policy, and there is a substantial body of literature addressing various aspects of this issue. Since the publication of Amartya Sen's (1999) seminal work on the capabilities approach to development, equal access to basic services has been recognized as a pivotal element to consider when dealing with issues such as poverty and deprivation (Filmer and Pritchett, 2001), gender equality (Kabeer, 2005; Scott et al., 2018), unequal regional development (Perrons, 2012), and sustainability (Burger and Christen, 2011). Access to basic services is especially relevant in the analysis of remote or marginalized areas, as for instance mountainous ones.

Basic services in mountainous areas

Basic services in mountainous areas refer to essential facilities and amenities required to meet the fundamental needs of the population residing in mountainous regions (UN, 2015). These services are crucial for the well-being and functioning of the communities in these areas and for making viable pathways of sustainable mountain development (Bracher et al., 2018). Key examples of basic services in mountainous areas include:

1. **Healthcare:** Access to healthcare facilities, including hospitals, clinics, and medical personnel, is vital in mountainous regions. Due to the challenging terrain and remoteness, it is important to have healthcare centers that can provide emergency care, primary healthcare services, and access to medication.
2. **Education:** Provision of educational facilities is crucial for the development of mountainous communities. Schools, both primary and secondary, should be established to ensure that children receive proper education. Depending on the remoteness of the area, boarding schools or alternative learning methods may be necessary.
3. **Water and Sanitation:** Access to clean drinking water and proper sanitation facilities is essential. In mountainous areas, the provision of safe drinking water may require the construction of infrastructure such as water treatment plants, reservoirs, and distribution systems. Sanitation facilities like toilets and waste management systems are also important to maintain hygiene.
4. **Electricity and Energy:** Mountainous regions may face challenges in accessing electricity due to the rugged terrain. Efforts should be made to extend electricity grids or provide alternative energy sources like solar power, wind energy, or micro-hydro systems to ensure reliable and sustainable energy supply to the communities.
5. **Transportation:** Establishing reliable transportation infrastructure is crucial in mountainous areas. This includes well-maintained roads, bridges, and tunnels that connect the remote communities to urban centers, enabling access to markets, healthcare, education, and other essential services.
6. **Communication:** Access to reliable communication networks, such as telephone and internet services, is important for connectivity in mountainous areas. This enables communication between communities, emergency services, and access to information and resources.
7. **Public Safety:** Mountainous areas may face specific safety concerns, such as natural disasters like landslides, avalanches, or forest fires. Therefore, the provision of fire departments, search and rescue teams, and emergency response services becomes crucial to ensure the safety and well-being of the population.
8. **Retail and Basic Supplies:** Availability of basic supplies like groceries, fuel, and other essential items is necessary in mountainous areas. Establishing local markets or retail outlets can help meet the daily needs of the residents, reducing their dependency on distant urban centers.

These basic services are essential for the sustainable development and quality of life in mountainous areas, ensuring that the communities have access to the resources and facilities necessary for their well-being and prosperity.

Barriers to fair access to basic services in mountainous areas

Fair access to basic services in mountainous areas is an important issue that has been seldom addressed in academic literature. Mountainous regions often face unique challenges due to their rugged terrain, remoteness, and limited infrastructure. This can result in disparities in access to essential services such as healthcare, education, water, and sanitation, depending on the context object of the study. For instance, several studies have focused on understanding and addressing the barriers to fair access to basic services in mountain areas by highlighting the interplay between geographic and political issues. Indeed, the topography of mountainous regions poses significant challenges for the provision of basic services. Steep slopes, rocky terrain, and extreme weather conditions can make it difficult to build and maintain infrastructure like roads, bridges, and power supply networks. The distribution of limited amounts of both land suitable for human activities, resources and infrastructure can generate property-related tensions (public versus private property rights, Dax, 2020) or use-related conflicts among different actors (local communities, local recreationists, tourists, amenity migrants, see Nepal and Chipeniuk, 2005). This can hinder both the delivery of adequate services to mountain communities and their viability over time (Sikorski et al., 2021). Moreover, limited transportation infrastructure can isolate mountain communities, making it challenging to access essential services. Road networks may be inadequate or prone to landslides and other natural hazards. In some cases, aerial or cable-based transportation systems have been explored as alternatives to improve connectivity (see deliverable n. 16). Mountain areas also face a shortage of healthcare facilities and medical professionals. The geographical isolation can result in delayed emergency response, limited access to specialized care, and higher healthcare costs. This situation is aggravated by a generalized lack of health policies specifically designed for application in remote areas. Rechel et al. (2016), for instance, analyzed health policies in eight high-income countries, finding that only one country (Italy) has implemented a national policy on hospitals in remote regions. Access to quality education is crucial for mountain communities. However, the geographical isolation can make it difficult to establish schools and provide adequate educational resources (von Dach and Ruiz Peyré, 2020). Researchers highlight the importance of innovative approaches such as distance learning, mobile schools (Mangione and Cannella, 2021), and community-based education (Tomazzoli, 2020) initiatives to improve educational access in mountainous regions. Finally, climate change, reduced precipitations and droughts are increasingly threatening mountain communities. These may face difficulties in accessing clean water and adequate sanitation facilities, either for permanent residents or tourism demand. Limited water sources, contamination risks, and inadequate sanitation infrastructure can lead to economic loss (agriculture, tourism) and health issues (Stephan et al., 2021). Academic studies emphasize the need for sustainable water management practices, improved sanitation facilities, and community engagement in water resource management (Lebel et al., 2010). Overall, academic literature recognizes the importance of addressing fair access to basic services in mountainous areas through interdisciplinary research, collaboration between stakeholders, and context-specific interventions to overcome the challenges and improve the livelihoods of mountain communities.

Strategies to improve fair access to basic services in mountainous areas

Ensuring fair access to basic services in remote areas is therefore essential for pursuing a sustainable development while addressing disparities. Table 1 summarizes the main strategies and the corresponding actions that can be implemented to increase access to basic services in remote areas and in particular mountainous ones:

Objective	Strategy	Actions
Needs	Conduct a thorough needs	Engage with local communities to understand

Assessment	assessment to understand the specific requirements of the remote area. This assessment should consider factors such as healthcare, education, water and sanitation, energy, transportation, and communication	their specific needs, challenges, and cultural contexts. Involve community members in decision-making processes, planning, and implementation of basic services. This approach ensures that services are tailored to the local context and are more likely to be accepted and sustainable
Infrastructure Development	Invest in developing infrastructure that improves accessibility to remote areas. Focus on connecting remote communities to larger towns or urban centers to facilitate the delivery of basic services	Building roads, bridges, and transportation networks to enhance accessibility. Improving access to reliable electricity, clean water, and sanitation facilities is also crucial for delivering basic services effectively
Mobile Service Delivery	Utilize mobile service delivery approaches to reach remote communities.	Deploying mobile clinics, libraries, or banking services to provide basic healthcare, educational resources, and financial services. Mobile service delivery can overcome the challenges of distance and limited infrastructure
Telecommunication Technologies	Enhance access to telecommunication technologies. This allows remote communities to access information, communication, and online services.	Leverage telecommunication technologies, such as mobile networks and internet connectivity, to facilitate communication and access to services in mountainous areas. Telemedicine, tele-education, and remote employment opportunities are examples of services that can be delivered remotely using digital platforms, improving accessibility and efficiency
Subsidies and Financial Incentives	Implement targeted subsidies or financial incentives to encourage service providers to operate in remote areas. This can attract private sector participation and bridge the affordability gap, making basic services more accessible and affordable for the local population	Develop supportive policies and regulatory frameworks that prioritize fair access to basic services in remote areas. Ensure that policies address the specific challenges faced by remote communities and promote equitable service delivery
Community Empowerment	Empower local communities to actively participate in decision-making and service delivery processes.	Engage community members in planning, implementing, and managing basic services through bottom-up approaches. Foster community ownership, involvement, and accountability to ensure fair access and sustainability
Local Development	Emphasize sustainable solutions that address long-term needs and promote resilience.	Mountain areas are often rich in biodiversity and provide critical ecosystem services. Balancing development initiatives with environmental conservation is essential to ensure the long-term well-being of mountain communities. Academic literature emphasizes the need for sustainable development strategies that take into account the ecological fragility of mountain ecosystems. For example, implementing renewable energy solutions like

		solar power can provide reliable electricity in remote mountainous areas. Sustainable agricultural practices and eco-tourism initiatives can also contribute to economic development and the overall well-being of the community
Public-Private Partnerships	Foster collaborations between public and private sectors to leverage resources, expertise, and innovation. Public-private partnerships can help overcome financial and operational challenges in delivering basic services in remote areas. They can also ensure that services are affordable, reliable, and sustainable.	Increase collaboration among different sectors, including government agencies, non-profit organizations, and private entities. Collaboration allows pooling of resources, expertise, and knowledge to address complex challenges and provide comprehensive basic services in mountainous areas. This approach can lead to more efficient service delivery and better outcomes
Capacity Building	Invest in capacity building programs for local communities and service providers in remote areas. Provide training and skills development opportunities that empower individuals to participate in service delivery and management. This helps build local capabilities and promotes self-sufficiency	Invest in training and capacity building programs for local communities and service providers in mountainous areas. This empowers individuals to actively participate in service delivery and management. Training programs can focus on healthcare workers, teachers, community leaders, and local entrepreneurs, enabling them to provide essential services and promote self-sustainability
Monitoring and Evaluation	Establish monitoring and evaluation mechanisms to assess the effectiveness and impact of interventions.	Regularly review and assess service delivery outcomes to identify gaps and make necessary adjustments to improve access and address inequalities

Table 1. Strategies and actions to explore solutions to improve fair access to basic services in mountainous areas.

Implementing these strategies requires collaboration among various stakeholders, including government agencies, community organizations, NGOs, and private sector entities. By adopting a comprehensive approach, that addresses infrastructure, technology, community involvement, and policy frameworks, fair access to basic services in remote areas can be improved, contributing to equitable development and improved quality of life.

Best practices and innovative models

As discussed in the previous sections, providing basic services in mountainous areas can be challenging due to the geographical barriers and limited infrastructure. However, there are several best practices that can help overcome these challenges and ensure the delivery of essential services. The academic literature has shown the potential that some innovative models and approaches have to increase access to basic services in marginal areas, such as mountainous ones:

1. **Mobile Technology and Telemedicine:** Leveraging mobile phones and telecommunication networks to provide healthcare services, health education, and remote consultations in underserved areas. This approach enables health workers to reach remote populations and provide medical advice, diagnosis, and treatment (see section 6).
2. **Community Health Workers (CHWs):** Training and deploying community members as CHWs who provide basic healthcare services, health education, and referrals to marginalized populations. CHWs act as a bridge between the community and the formal healthcare system, increasing access to healthcare in underserved areas. (WHO, 2020)

3. Microfinance and Microcredit: Utilizing microfinance institutions and microcredit programs to provide financial services to individuals and small businesses in marginalized areas. This approach enables the establishment and growth of small enterprises that can provide essential services such as water management systems and energy solutions. (Manta, 2022)
4. Social Entrepreneurship: Encouraging the development of social enterprises that focus on delivering essential services to marginalized areas. These enterprises often employ innovative business models to provide affordable and sustainable access to goods, as for instance food, and services like energy, water, education, and healthcare (Osti, 2012).
5. Public-Private Partnerships (PPPs): Collaborations between public and private entities to improve service delivery in marginalized areas. PPPs can combine the resources, expertise, and innovation of both sectors to develop and manage infrastructure, such as schools, healthcare facilities, and utilities, while generating opportunities for the development of mountain economies (Weiermair et al., 2008).
6. Frugal Innovation: Developing cost-effective and resource-efficient solutions that cater to the specific needs and constraints of marginalized areas. Frugal innovations focus on simplicity, affordability, and adaptability, allowing for the provision of basic services in resource-constrained settings. (Rosca et al., 2018)
7. Social Impact Bonds: Implementing outcome-based financing mechanisms where private investors provide upfront capital for social service programs in marginalized areas. Returns on investment are contingent on achieving predefined social outcomes, ensuring accountability and efficiency in service delivery. (Corvo and Pastore, 2019)
8. Off-Grid Energy Solutions: Harnessing renewable energy technologies, such as solar panels and mini-grids, to provide electricity in remote and marginalized areas. These solutions enable access to lighting, clean cooking, and power for basic services, improving quality of life and enabling economic opportunities (Ferrari et al., 2018).

While these models have shown promise, their effectiveness may vary depending on the context and specific needs of the marginalized areas. Therefore, it is crucial to conduct thorough assessments and engage with local stakeholders to identify and implement the most appropriate strategies for delivering basic services effectively.

The assessment framework

The purpose of this study is to identify specific areas within the Valle d'Aosta region and determine the population residing in those areas that may benefit from a collective on-demand mobility service. This service would complement the existing public transportation options and ensure equal access to essential services. All the municipalities in the Valle d'Aosta region are categorized as mountainous areas, resulting in a lower population density and a concentration of the population in the areas situated on the valley floor. The following analyses have been realized to achieve this goal:

- [demographic and socio-economic analysis](#) to provide an overall understanding of the entire region. This analysis includes the examination and mapping of various demographic and socioeconomic indicators at the municipal level.
- [cluster analysis](#), leveraging the demographic and socio-economic territorial information collected, to identify the municipalities that can be considered mobility generators, mobility-demanding areas and vulnerable territories.

Demographic and socio-economic context of analysis

The primary objective of the analysis is to assess the accessibility of basic services, so indicators related to basic services that generate mobility demand have been identified. The selection criteria for these basic services were established based on the broader concept of "internal area". The identification of internal areas stems from a polycentric approach to the territory, which means a network of municipalities or groups of municipalities (*service supply centres*) around which areas with varying degrees of spatial peripherality revolve. In this meaning, *Internal areas*, refer to parts of the territory located significantly far from the centers providing essential services¹. Throughout the region, about 72% of the territory is considered inland areas (including 55% intermediate and 17% peripheral).

Figure 1. Map of the territorial hierarchy according to the methodological classification for the recognition of "Inland Areas".

Source: elaboration on data provided by Minister for European Affairs, the South, Cohesion Policies and PNRR

¹ This definition is reported in the technical document of the Partnership Agreement "National Strategy for Internal Areas" which was produced in 2013 by the Agency for Territorial Cohesion, headed by the homonymous Ministry

These areas lack the necessary "pre-conditions of development," which refers to the availability of services considered fundamental rights of "citizenship" in contemporary society, namely: healthcare, vocational education and training, and mobility, as main factors among those identified in the previous paragraphs. Considering this, the present analysis has focused on those services related to health and education due to their crucial role in the lives of citizens who, due to the absence of these services in their residing areas, are compelled to travel to the centers that offer them. The study already focuses and tries to act directly on the third element, namely mobility. Table 2 provides a comprehensive list of the selected variable indicators for the demographic and socio-economic analysis, suitably organized into the following thematic macro-categories: Demography (9 indicators), Level of education (4 indicators), Employment condition (7 indicators), Active enterprises and employees (8 indicators), Mobility (5 indicators), Tourism (6 indicators).

Macro-category	Code	Indicator	Data Source	Years considered	Geographic level	Description and calculation
Demography	I.1	Population 0-9 years	Istat	2019	Municipality	The data includes the residents' population of each municipality between 0 and 9 years
	I.2	Population 10-19 years	Istat	2019	Municipality	The data includes the residents' population of each municipality, between 10 and 19 years
	I.3	Population 20-64 years	Istat	2019	Municipality	The data includes the residents' population of each municipality, between 20 and 64 years
	I.4	Population over 65 years	Istat	2019	Municipality	The data includes the residents' population of each municipality, over 65 years
	I.5	Total population	OES VdA ²	2021	Municipality	The data includes the total residents' population of each municipality
				2021	Unités des Communes	The data includes the total residents' population in the Unités des Communes in the Aosta Valley
	I.6	Old age index (>65)	OES VdA	2021	Municipality	Old age (index of), indicates the degree of ageing of the population. It is obtained by dividing the amount of elderly population (65 years and over) by the amount of young people (0 to 19 years), per 100. The index tells us how many older people there are for every 100 younger people.
					Unités des Communes	Old age (index of), indicates the degree of ageing of the population. It is obtained by

² [Economic and Social Monitoring Centre](#)

						dividing the amount of elderly population (65 years and over) by the amount of young people (0 to 19 years), per 100. The index tells us how many older people there are for every 100 younger people.
	1.7	Old age index (>85)	Istat	2019	Municipality	Old age (index of), indicates the degree of ageing of the population. It is obtained by dividing the amount of elderly population (85 years and over) by the amount of young people (0 to 19 years), per 100. The index tells us how many older people there are for every 100 younger people.
	1.8	Structural dependency index	OES VdA	2021	Municipality	Structural dependency (index of): ratio of non-working age population (0-14 years and 65 years and over) to working age population (15-64 years) multiplied by 100. It, therefore, calculates how many individuals there are of non-working age for every 100 of working age, indirectly providing a measure of the sustainability of a population structure.
Unit of the Municipalities					Structural dependency (index of): ratio of non-working age population (0-14 years and 65 years and over) to working age population (15-64 years) multiplied by 100. It, therefore, calculates how many individuals there are of non-working age for every 100 of working age, indirectly providing a measure of the sustainability of a population structure.	
	1.9	Youthfulness index	Istat	2019	Municipality	Youthfulness (index of): expresses the number of children and young people up to the age of 14 present per 100 elderly people aged 65 and over. A value of 100 indicates, according to the index, a perfect numerical balance between the older and younger generation.
	1.10	Population trend	Istat - OES VdA	2011/2021	Municipality	The demographic trend over the ten-year interval (2011-2021) was calculated as: (POPULATION TO 2021 -

						POPULATION TO 2011) / POPULATION TO 2011 * 100. The resulting value expresses negative (decrease) or positive (increase) population values over the analysed period.
	I.11	Population density	OES VdA	2021	Municipality	The data derived from the calculation of the ratio of total population to municipal surface area
Level of education	II.1	Illiterates and literates without educational qualifications	Istat	2019	Municipality	Resident population aged 6 years and over who cannot read or write or who can read and write but lack educational qualifications
	II.2	Primary and middle school diploma	Istat	2019	Municipality	Resident population aged 6 years and over with a primary and middle school diploma
	II.3	Secondary education diploma	Istat	2019	Municipality	Resident population aged 6 years and over with a secondary education diploma
	II.4	Tertiary degree, university diploma, doctorate	Istat	2019	Municipality	Resident population aged 6 years and over with a tertiary education diploma (non-university tertiary degree, university degree, doctoral degree)
Employment condition	III.1	Employed	Istat	2019	Municipality	Resident population aged 15 years and over who carry out regular work activity and is actively looking for employment
	III.2	Unemployed	Istat	2019	Municipality	Resident population aged 15 years and over who don't carry out a regular work activity
	III.3	Retired	Istat	2019	Municipality	Resident population aged 15 years and over. It includes those who have ceased working due to age, disability or other causes; it does not necessarily coincide with a pensioner (i.e. enjoys a pension)
	III.4	Students	Istat	2019	Municipality	Persons aged 6 years or older who are enrolled in primary school, secondary school, university
	III.5	Housewives/Homemakers	Istat	2019	Municipality	Resident population is mainly engaged in household chores

	III.6	In other conditions	Istat	2019	Municipality	Resident population who is in a condition other than those listed above (unfit for work, well-off, etc.)
	III.7	Unemployment rate	Istat	2019	Municipality	Calculated as the ratio of the unemployed aged 15-74 to the active population obtained as the sum of the numerator and the total employed multiplied by 100.
Active enterprises and employees	IV.1	Active enterprises	Istat	2020	Municipality	The data includes the total number of active enterprises located in the municipality
	IV.2	Employees in active enterprises	Istat	2020	Municipality	The data includes the total number of employees in active enterprises located in the municipality
	IV.3	Active micro enterprises	Istat	2020	Municipality	The data includes the total number of active micro-enterprises located in the municipality
	IV.4	Active small enterprises	Istat	2020	Municipality	The data includes the total number of active small enterprises located in the municipality
	IV.5	Active medium and big enterprises	Istat	2020	Municipality	The data includes the total number of active medium enterprises located in the municipality
	IV.6	Employees in active micro enterprises	Istat	2020	Municipality	The data includes the total number of employees in active micro-enterprises located in the municipality
	IV.7	Employees in small active enterprises	Istat	2020	Municipality	The data includes the total number of employees in active small enterprises located in the municipality
	IV.8	Employees in medium and big active enterprises	Istat	2020	Municipality	The data includes the total number of employees in active medium and big enterprises located in the municipality
Mobility	V.1	Daily commuters from their municipalities	OES VdA	2019	Municipality	The data includes the resident population that moves daily by the resident municipality, calculated based on the percentage incidence of the total resident population
	V.2	Daily commuters for study	OES VdA	2019	Municipality	The data includes the resident population that moves daily by the resident municipality for study
	V.3	Daily commuters for work	OES VdA	2019	Municipality	The data includes the resident population that moves daily by the resident municipality for work

	V.4	Motorization rate	Istat	2018	Municipality	The motorisation rate expresses the ratio of registered car fleet per municipality to the number of residents in the same municipality. This expresses the average number of cars per capita
Tourism	VI.1	Italian touristic arrivals	Istat	2022	Municipality	The data includes the total number of Italian touristic arrivals
	VI.2	Foreign touristic arrivals	Istat	2022	Municipality	The data includes the total number of foreign touristic arrivals
	VI.3	Italian touristic presences	Istat	2022	Municipality	The data includes the total number of Italian touristic presence
	VI.4	Foreign touristic presences	Istat	2022	Municipality	The data includes the total number of foreign touristic presence
	VI.5	Accommodations	Istat	2022	Municipality	The data includes the total number of accommodations
	VI.6	Beds in the accommodations	Istat	2022	Municipality	The data includes the total number of beds in the accommodations
Basic services to citizens	VII.1	Schools	Istat / MIUR ³	2023	Municipality	The data includes the total number of school facilities
	VII.2	Students	DSS ⁴ VdA	2023	Municipality	The data includes the number of people who study within the municipality, even if they reside in other municipalities
	VII.3	Social-welfare Facilities	OES VdA	2020	Municipality	The data includes the total number of social welfare facilities in the municipality. Types includes: kindergarten, veterinary clinics, family homes, health spas, Alzheimer's residential unit, diagnostic imaging, sports medicine, day centres for the disabled
	VII.4	Health-care Facilities	OES VdA	2020	Municipality	This data includes the total number of traditional hospital facilities
	VII.5	Guests of social-welfare facilities	OES VdA	2020	Municipality	The data includes the total number of people hosted in social-welfare facilities.

³ [Ministry of Education and Merit](#)

⁴ [Department superintendence of studies](#)

	VII.6	Guests of health-care facilities	OES VdA	2020	Municipality	The data includes the total number of people hosted in health-care facilities.
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Table 2. Selected indicators for the analysis of the socio-demographic and economic context of the Valle d'Aosta region.

The analysis was carried out by collecting the data and representing them through tables, graphs and maps.

Cluster analysis

As mentioned earlier, in the introductory section before and during the presentation of the collected indicators, the question of how to systematise and give a key to interpretation to this fairly numerous set of indicators was posed for this analysis. The statistical analysis was repeated for the three macro-categories of indicators, which will be presented shortly, and which set the three keys to understanding the original research question.

The statistical method used is that of hierarchical cluster analysis:

- It produces a set of clusters organized as a hierarchical tree.
- Can be visualized as a dendrogram or tree diagram showing the sequence of mergers between clusters.
- Different values on the ordinates can correspond to clustering composed of a different number of elements.

There are two approaches for creating a hierarchical clustering:

1. Agglomerative:
 - a. Start with clusters consisting of single elements.
 - b. At each step, merge the two 'closest' clusters until there remains a single cluster (or k clusters).
2. Divisive:
 - a. Starts with a single cluster that includes all elements.
 - b. At each step, split the 'furthest' cluster until the clusters contain only one element (or k clusters are created).
 - Normally hierarchical algorithms use a similarity or distance matrix (proximity matrix)

For this study, the approach used was the *Agglomerative* approach, which allowed the municipalities to be grouped into 6 clusters. Throughout this analytical phase, the municipality of Aosta was excluded from the variables as it is considered as an outlier due to its values being too distant from all other municipalities. From an initial analysis, in fact, this was always isolated and thus constituted a cluster in itself, so to avoid statistical distortions it was excluded from the analysis, also because as a capital it presents urban characteristics both physical and functional that qualify it as a large city, thus far from the principle that moves the entire logical flow of the study at a quantitative level.

Thus, in this second phase, a statistical approach is used to categorize and then group the municipalities by similarity according to the macro-families of indicators that we will now illustrate.

The proposed approach uses the clustering algorithm, that starting from the complete dataset, presented in Table 2, is applied into the following three macro-categories each containing a subset of indicators:

- “mobility generators”: are entities, facilities, or factors that contribute to generating the demand for transportation or mobility. These are elements or activities that attract people and result in the need for movement from one location to another. Mobility generators play a significant role in shaping travel patterns and transportation infrastructure

planning. The macro-category includes indicators related to the presence and consistency of the healthcare facilities, educational institutions and companies (micro and SMEs).

- “mobility demand”: refers to the need or desire for transportation or movement from one location to another. It represents the collective requirement for travel by individuals or groups to access goods, services, activities, or destinations. The macro-category includes indicators related to the commuters for work, commuters for school and tourist presences.
- “vulnerability”: refers to the susceptibility of the local population living in mountainous regions to various social, economic, and environmental challenges. Mountainous areas present unique characteristics and conditions that can exacerbate vulnerability and hinder access to resources, services, and opportunities (e.g. geographic isolation, limited infrastructure and services). The macro-category includes indicators related to the population trend, density, old age index and youthfulness index.

Macro-category	Code	Indicator	Justification
Mobility generators	IV.3	Active micro enterprises	It represents small neighbourhood trade and family-run businesses (less than 10 employees), providing an estimate of the extent to which municipalities are supplied with these small businesses that typically generate short-movement phenomena
	IV.4	Active small enterprises	It represents the small companies (over 10 employees and under 50) that can attract a fairly modest number of workers or customers who can move even outside their municipality to reach them
	IV.5	Active medium and big enterprises	It represents medium and large companies that are great mobility attractors, especially for the high number of employees that can generate large flows of daily trips (especially during peak hours)
	IV.2	Employees	Number of employees employed in all types of businesses (micro, small, medium and large) who potentially commute from home to work each day, providing an indirect estimate of the amount of activity in the municipality (except in the case of smart workers)
	VII.1	Schools	Schools and universities that attract students, faculty, and staff. These institutions can generate transportation demand, especially during the start and end of school / academic sessions
	VII.2	Students	It represents the number of students enrolled in the municipality's educational/academic establishments and therefore who reach the school sites also from other municipalities
	VII.3	Social-welfare Facilities	Social welfare facilities serve a wide catchment area. People travel to these facilities resulting in transportation demand
	VII.5	Guests of social-welfare facilities	It represents an estimate of the people moving to these facilities resulting in a transportation demand
	VII.4	Health-care facilities	Hospitals, clinics, and medical centres that serve a wide catchment area. People travel to these facilities for medical appointments, treatments, and emergencies, resulting in transportation demand
	VII.6	Guests of health-	It represents an estimate of the catchment area

		care facilities	that on average is hospitalized providing an idea of the importance of the service and therefore of the related movements it can generate (patient visits, visiting family members, staff, health personnel), resulting in transportation demand
Mobility demand	I.1	Population 0-9 years	It represents the number of individuals who make up the younger class of the population and who need to move almost always in the company
	I.2	Population 10-19 years	It represents the number of individuals that potentially can move alone for study or leisure purposes
	I.3	Population 20-64 years	It represents the population of working age who need to move for work, study or leisure reasons
	I.4	Population over 65 years	It represents the number of individuals of retirement age who mainly need to move for leisure, medical visits or errands
	I.5	Total population	It represents the Figure of the maximum potential pool of individuals who need to move for various reasons
	V.2	Daily commuters for study	It represents the number of commuters who leave their municipality of residence each day for educational purposes
	V.3	Daily commuters for work	It represents the number of commuters who leave their municipality of residence each day for work reasons
	VI.5	Accommodations	Number of tourist accommodation facilities within each municipality, reflecting the degree of tourist attractiveness of the municipality
	VI.3 + VI.4	Touristic presences	It represents the number of annual tourists in the municipality who potentially may need to move from the municipality
	V.4	Motorization rate	It represents the per capita ownership of the car thus highlighting the degree of dependence on private cars of municipalities' population
Vulnerability	I.10	Population trend (2011-2021)	It represents the trend of growth or decrease of the population in a decade summarizing the natural and migratory balance of each municipality and highlighting depopulation phenomena
	I.11	Population density	It provides the diffusion of the population to the municipal extension, allowing to identify of the municipalities characterized by small inhabited nucleus or by larger urban centres
	I.9	Youthfulness index	It represents the degree of youth of the population residing in the municipality, useful to understand
	I.6	Old age index	This figure shows the degree of old age of the population residing in the municipality, useful for understanding which type and mode of mobility service could be more appropriate.
	I.7	Old age index (>85)	It represents the degree of great seniority of the resident population, which may no longer be able to move independently

Table 3. Provides the list of the macro-categories and the corresponding indicators included in each. It also includes a descriptive explanation justifying why these indicators were selected.

Demographic and socio-economic assessment of the Valle d'Aosta region

Demography

Figure 2. Population between 0 and 9 years. Source: own elaboration on data provided by ISTAT, 2019 (Indicator I.1)

Figure 3. Map of population between 10 and 19 years. Source: own elaboration on data provided by ISTAT, 2019 (Indicator I.2)

Figure 4. Map of population between 20 and 64 years. Source: own elaboration on data provided by ISTAT, 2019 (Indicator I.3)

Figure 5. Map of population over 65 years. Source: own elaboration on data provided by ISTAT, 2019 (Indicator I.4)

Figure 6. Map of resident population for each municipality. Source: own elaboration on data provided by OES VdA, 2021 (Indicator I.5)

Figure 7. Map of Old Age Index over 65 for each municipality. Source: own elaboration on data provided by OES VdA, 2021 (Indicator I.6)

Figure 8. Map of Old Age Index over 85 for each municipality.
Source: own elaboration on data provided by ISTAT, 2019 (Indicator I.7)

Figure 9. Map of structural dependency index. Source: own elaboration on data provided by OES VdA, 2021 (Indicator I.8)

Figure 10. Map of youthfulness index for each municipality.
Source: own elaboration on data provided by ISTAT, 2019 (Indicator I.9)

Figure 11. Map of the demographic trend index. Source: own elaboration on data provided by ISTAT and OES VdA, inter-annual. (Indicator I.10)

Figure 12. Map of population density index. Source: own elaboration on data provided by OES VdA, 2021. (Indicator I.11)

Valle d'Aosta region is entirely mountainous and belongs to the mountain system of the Western Alps, whose advantageous physical position has promoted a considerably earlier and more intensive populating process throughout time than other mountainous macro-regions.

Approximately 80% of its land area is covered by rural regions, which are mostly unaffected by the detrimental impacts of strong urbanization processes (Istat, 2021).

The municipal detail of the data provided by the Economic and Economic Observatory (OES) of the Autonomous Valle d'Aosta region has made it possible to develop the analyses of this part for the nine "*Unités des Communes valdôtaines*" (also associating Aosta with the 8 Unités) thus giving a synthetic quantitative picture of the demographic dynamics (Ceccarelli, 2017). It was decided not to propose any further territorial aggregations of municipalities, as the comparison of demographic issues for units and territorial areas had already been thoroughly explored. However, the availability of data at the municipal territorial scale has facilitated the creation of supplementary paragraphs accompanied by maps. These maps provide a visual representation of the spatial dynamics of the variables considered in the analysis of economic and social contexts, allowing for an immediate understanding.

The resident population is predominantly distributed along the central longitudinal axis of the Region. The municipalities with the highest population densities (excluding the capital city of Aosta) include Saint-Pierre, Sarre, Gressan, Saint Christophe, Nus, Saint Vincent, Chatillon, and Pont Saint Martin, with populations ranging from 2,800 to 5,500 inhabitants. In all other municipalities, the population is relatively sparse due to specific geographical and altimetric characteristics. These characteristics, coupled with a tendency towards depopulation, particularly in small *nuclei* located in the higher valleys, contribute to the sparse population distribution.

For years, the entire national territory has experienced an aging population due to an increase in the proportion of elderly individuals resulting from improved longevity and a decline in birth rates, despite contributions from migratory flows.

The spatial distribution of the population aged nine and under follows a similar pattern to that of the total population. Notably, there is a widespread scarcity of young people throughout the region.

The most significant observation from these maps is not merely the presence of population within different age groups, but rather the progressive increase in the number of individuals falling into higher age brackets. This demonstrates a progressive aging of the population, which is a trend observed throughout Italy, indicating a lack of generational replacement.

Among the Unités des Communes, Aosta consistently exhibits the highest old-age indices throughout the analysis period, reaching a peak of 227.6 individuals over the age of sixty-five per 100 children on January 1, 2020. The Unité Mont-Rose also shows high indices, closely approaching those of Aosta starting from 2016, with a maximum of 221.7 elderly individuals per 100 children on January 1, 2020. On the other end of the spectrum, the Grand-Combin and Mont-Émilis Units have the lowest old-age indices. As of January 1, 2020, Grand-Combin had 161.6 elderly individuals per 100 children, and Mont-Émilis had 143.2. However, it is noteworthy that the Unité Grand-Combin experienced a relative increase in the old-age index, rising from 118.9 to 161.6.

What remains consistent across all Units is the growing imbalance between the elderly and children observed throughout the entire region.

Lastly, it is striking to observe the constant positive deviation between Unité Aosta and the regional and national average values. Although less pronounced, a positive gap also exists between the values of the Unités Mont-Rose and Walser and the reference values of the region and the country of Italy.

Among other structural indicators, the dependency index, which considers the population of non-working age (under 14 and over 65) in relation to the "productive" age group (15-64 years), allows for an analysis of the relationship between the youth, elderly, and working-age components of Valle d'Aosta and its infra-regional aggregations. The index is compared to the values of Italy as a whole and the North-West region. Unlike the old-age index, the dependency index clearly highlights the increasing burden of supporting those who do not contribute economically (the young and the old), as their needs are borne by the productive part of the

population (adults). It is important to note that the youth dependency ratio and the old-age dependency ratio have distinct meanings and future consequences. While a high old-age dependency ratio indicates the challenges of an aging population, a high youth dependency ratio can be seen as an investment in a future population structure that will be more substantial (Bonifazi et al., 2019).

The dependency index for the Aosta Valley (see Figure 13) shows values above the national average in both 2020 and 2011 (59.0 compared to 56.7 in 2020 and 53.9 compared to 52.7 in 2011). Consistent with the findings of the old-age index, Unité Aosta has the highest dependency ratio in 2020 (66.9 compared to the regional average of 59.0), while Unité Mont-Émilius has the lowest dependency ratio (52.9 individuals of non-working age for every 100 individuals aged between 15 and 64).

Figure 13. Dependency ratio for young people, the elderly, the structural - Italy, North-West, Valle d'Aosta and Unités des Communes, 2011, 2020. Source: own elaboration on data provided by the Economic and Social Observatory – Autonomous Region of Valle d'Aosta and ISTAT data.

In all Units, the dependency ratio of the elderly is higher than that of the juveniles, indicating the significant and widespread aging of the population in Valle d'Aosta. Furthermore, when compared to 2011, there has been a deterioration in the indicator across all analyzed Units. Taking Unité Aosta as an example, the overall index has increased from 59.8 to 66.9. This increase is primarily driven by the elderly component, with the dependency ratio of the elderly rising from 39.7 to 46.5, while the youth component shows a slight variation from 20.1 to 20.4.

Looking at the territorial areas, Aosta maintains its prominence (see Figure 13). It is followed by the areas Polo bassa valle (61.1) and Alta montagna non turistica (59.4). However, there is a distinction among these three territorial areas: while Aosta and Polo bassa valle have a youth

dependency index close to 20 (meaning there are 20 individuals under the age of 14 per 100 inhabitants aged 15-64 years), the Alta montagna non-tourist area has a lower value (16.7 individuals under 14 years per 100 inhabitants aged 15-64 years). This discrepancy reflects the earlier observations regarding the limited presence of youth in the region.

Figure 14. Youth dependency ratio, elderly, structural by territorial areas, 1.1.2020. Source: elaborations on data provided by the Economic and Social Observatory – Autonomous Region of Valle d'Aosta and Istat data.

The population aged 65 and over represents approximately a quarter of the total resident population at the regional level (24.2%). As of January 1, 2020, there were over 30,300 elderly residents, with the majority concentrated in the 65-74 age group (11.8%). Compared to 2011, the region has seen an increase of over 3,500 elderly individuals (+13.3%). This increase is observed across all age groups analyzed, with approximately a 1-percentage-point increase in each of the three categories at the regional level. As previously mentioned in the study of structural indicators, Aosta has a higher proportion of elderly individuals, with residents aged 65 and over representing 27.8% in 2020.

Regarding the subgroup of the elderly aged 85 and over, their relative weight in the population varies from a minimum of 2.8% in Unité Mont-Émilis to a maximum of 4.9% in Aosta.

Considering the significant impact of the aging process across both the Italian territory and the Valle d'Aosta Region, it is important to further examine this focus, particularly in relation to the territorial areas. These areas include high mountain regions where the infrastructure and terrain characteristics could exacerbate the negative consequences of these structural changes.

Level of education

Figure 15. Map of illiterates and literates without educational qualifications. Source: own elaboration on data provided by ISTAT, 2019 (Indicator II.1)

Figure 16. Map of resident population with primary and middle school diploma. Source: own elaboration on data provided by ISTAT, 2019 (Indicator II.2)

Figure 17. Map of resident population with a secondary education diploma. Source: own elaboration on data provided by ISTAT, 2019 (Indicator II.3)

Figure 18. Map of resident population with a tertiary education diploma. Source: own elaboration on data provided by ISTAT, 2019 (Indicator II.4)

Information on the level of education provides valuable insights into demographic characteristics, particularly highlighting areas where educational attainment and the degree of education tend to be lower based on the territorial context. Analyzing data on the population's educational qualifications allows us to interpret the impact of distance from services and isolation on educational development. Surveys indicate that there are still numerous municipalities with a significant number of illiterate individuals, as well as those who have completed only primary or middle school education.

Regarding the population that has completed secondary-level education, the numbers are relatively good, considering that in most of the territory (excluding the municipalities of Chamois, Bard, La Magdaleine, Pontboset, and Remes-Notre-Dame), the proportion of individuals with this qualification is moderately acceptable. However, the same cannot be said for the population that pursued higher education, including specializations and degrees. In fact, most municipalities in the northern part of the region, as well as those in the southwest and southeast, have a low number of individuals with this level of education.

It is evident that the smaller municipalities, once again, provide fewer opportunities for the population to continue their studies, either due to a lack of desire to relocate or a lack of cultural resources necessary for pursuing higher education. Given that these contexts are often characterized by household economies, the focus tends to be on basic training throughout life and entering the workforce at a relatively young age, engaging in tasks that do not necessarily require higher education qualifications.

Employment condition

Figure 19. Map of employed index for each municipality.
Source: own elaboration on data provided by ISTAT, 2019
(Indicator III.1)

Figure 20. Map of unemployment index for each municipality.
Source: own elaboration on data provided by ISTAT, 2019
(Indicator III.2)

Figure 21. Map of retired index for each municipality. Source: own elaboration on data provided by ISTAT, 2019 (Indicator III.3)

Figure 22. Map of resident population enrolled in primary school, secondary school, university. Source: own elaboration on data provided by ISTAT, 2019 (Indicator III.4)

Figure 23. Map of resident population engaged in household chores. Source: own elaboration on data provided by ISTAT, 2019 (Indicator III.5)

Figure 24. Map of resident population in other conditions. Source: own elaboration on data provided by ISTAT, 2019 (Indicator III.6)

Figure 25. Map of unemployment rate index. Source: own elaboration on data provided by ISTAT, 2019 (Indicator III.7)

To accurately estimate the demand for mobility, it is crucial to first understand the socio-economic context that serves as the basis for implementing the journey estimation model.

As mentioned earlier, the selection of variables for this study is influenced by the research objectives, which aim to determine the population's daily mobility needs for various reasons, with work being the primary factor. The spatial distribution of the employed population aligns closely with the overall population distribution. The highest concentration of employed individuals is observed in Aosta, the capital city, and the neighboring municipalities along the main valley, including Saint-Cristophe, Sarre, Saint Pierre, Quart, Nus, and Gressan. Moving west along the border with France, the municipality of Courmayeur stands out as the only one in the highest category of employed individuals. Similarly, to the east of the capital, the cluster of municipalities around Chatillon, Saint Vincent, and Pont Saint Martin also falls into the same category. On the other hand, the unemployment index presents a relatively low value, as the Valle d'Aosta region has one of the lowest rates at the national level. However, when analysing the dynamics at the municipal level, three main macro-areas with higher unemployment rates become apparent.

The first macro-area is in the northwestern part, encompassing municipalities around Pré Saint Didier, which has the highest unemployment rate. The other two macro-areas are located at the opposite eastern extremity of the region. In the northern part, there are municipalities such as Chamois, Valtournenche, Saint Vincent, and their neighbouring towns, which exhibit the highest unemployment rates. On the southern side of the eastern region, the municipalities around Verrés also have elevated unemployment rates.

Active enterprises and employees

Figure 26. Map of the total number of active enterprises.
Source: elaborations on data provided by ISTAT, 2020
(Indicator IV.1)

Figure 27. Map of the total number of employees in active enterprises.
Source: elaborations on data provided by ISTAT, 2020 (Indicator IV.2)

Figure 28. Map of the total number of active micro enterprises.
Source: elaborations on data provided by ISTAT, 2020
(Indicator IV.3)

Figure 29. Map of the total number of active small enterprises.
Source: elaborations on data provided by ISTAT, 2020
(Indicator IV.4)

Figure 30. Map of the total number of active medium and big enterprises.
Source: elaborations on data provided by ISTAT, 2020 (Indicator IV.5)

Figure 31. Map of the total number of employees in active micro enterprise.
Source: elaborations on data provided by ISTAT, 2020 (Indicator IV.6)

Figure 32. Map of the total number of employees in small active enterprises.
Source: elaboration on data provided by ISTAT, 2020 (Indicator IV.7)

Figure 33. Map of the total number of employees in medium and big active enterprises.
Source: elaboration on data provided by ISTAT, 2020 (Indicator IV.8)

In addition to socio-economic factors, the distribution of companies throughout the region is also considered in the analysis. The provided data includes the number of employees for each company, which was aggregated based on company size classification (micro, small, medium, large) in order to synthesize and represent the information on the map.

For the purpose of this analysis, the focus was primarily on small enterprises (up to 50 employees), while medium-sized (up to 250 employees) and large enterprises were grouped together on a separate map. The map of small businesses shows a concentration of a high number of such enterprises in the capital city of Aosta. Other municipalities such as Courmayeur, Quart, Saint Christophe, Saint Vincent, and Pontboset fall into the second-highest class, indicating a moderate number of small businesses (10 to 21 companies). This map highlights the influence of accessibility and the presence of basic services, driven by the population, on the allocation and location preferences of companies over time.

The pattern is similar for medium and large enterprises, with a concentration in three macro-aggregations of municipalities. The first aggregation is in the upper valley, centered around Courmayeur. The second aggregation is around Aosta, the capital city. The third aggregation is along the northern and southern fringes of Saint Vincent. Although the absolute number of companies decreases significantly for medium and large enterprises, the importance of each

company in terms of catchment areas is crucial. These macro-aggregations play a decisive role in evaluating the attractiveness and demand for mobility in the respective areas.

Mobility

Figure 34. Map of resident population that moves daily by the resident municipality. Source: elaborations on data provided by OES VdA, 2019. (Indicator V.1)

Figure 35. Map of resident population that moves daily by the resident municipality for study. Source: elaboration on data provided by OES VdA, 2019. (Indicator V.2)

Figure 36. Map of resident population that moves daily by the resident municipality for work. Source: elaboration on data provided by OES VdA, 2019. (Indicator V.3)

Figure 37. Map of motorisation rate. Source: elaboration on data provided by OES VdA, 2018. (Indicator V.4)

The spatial distribution of workers is influenced by numerous factors, but for the purpose of this study, it is important to understand the extent to which individuals commute outside their municipality on a daily basis. However, it should be noted that the Transport Directorate of the Region has not yet implemented the Origins-Destinations matrix, which would provide precise information on commuting patterns.

Without access to the matrix, it is currently not possible to establish with precision the specific municipalities from which commuters originate and the destinations they travel to on a daily basis. The available data does not provide a comprehensive picture of commuting patterns within the region. However, it is worth noting that commuting behaviours can be influenced by various factors such as employment opportunities, proximity to workplaces, transportation infrastructure, and quality of services.

To obtain a more accurate understanding of commuter flows within the region, it would be necessary to establish and implement the Origins-Destinations matrix, which would provide detailed information on the commuting patterns of residents. This data would enable a more comprehensive analysis of mobility demands and assist in the planning and development of

transportation systems to meet the needs of commuters effectively⁵. The available data allows us to analyse the percentage of commuting on a municipal scale, providing insights into the commuting patterns within the region. It is observed that commuting is a prevalent reality throughout the region, with only a few municipalities having commuting rates below 30%, such as Rhemes Notre Dame and Chamois.

A concentration of municipalities with higher commuting rates can be seen around Aosta, ranging between 55% and 62%. This reflects the attractiveness of the capital city and its ability to generate employment opportunities that draw commuters from the surrounding municipalities. Commuting is predominantly driven by two main reasons: work and study. By analysing the percentage of trips for these purposes, it becomes apparent which territories have a higher proportion of commuters in each category. The municipalities around the capital exhibit a higher percentage of trips for work compared to study. This is consistent with the higher total percentage of commuters observed previously and can be attributed to the presence of educational institutions in the more populous municipalities, which may lack in remote mountain areas.

The motorization rate of the population is another indicator that contributes to understanding travel patterns. This rate is determined by the ratio of registered cars to the number of residents within a municipality, providing an average of car ownership per capita. The map reveals that most municipalities in the lower valley have a relatively high motorization rate, with approximately 80 cars per 100 inhabitants. The number of cars increases in municipalities close to the capital, likely linked to the economic prosperity of these areas. Notably, two municipalities in the upper valley (Rhemes Notre Dame to the south and Courmayeur to the north) exhibit a relatively high motorization rate, influencing neighbouring municipalities. Conversely, the southern belt of the central valley shows lower motorization rates, suggesting that a public transport service may be more beneficial in this region.

These insights into commuting patterns, the purpose of travel (work or study), and the motorization rate of the population contribute to the overall understanding of travel behaviours and transportation needs within the region.

Tourism

Figure 38. Map of the total number of Italian touristic arrival.
Source: elaborations on data provided by OES VdA, 2022
(Indicator VI.1)

Figure 39. Map of the total number of foreign touristic arrivals.
Source: elaborations on data provided by OES VdA, 2022
(Indicator VI.2)

⁵ As will be discussed in more detail in the following report, the analysis of inter-municipal flows was estimated from the Origin-Destination matrix compiled by ISTAT as of 2011.

Figure 40. Map of the total number of Italian touristic presence.
Source: elaborations on data provided by OES VdA, 2022
(Indicator VI.3)

Figure 41. Map the total number of foreign touristic presence.
Source: elaborations on data provided by OES VdA, 2022
(Indicator VI.4)

Figure 42. Map of the total number of accommodations.
Source: elaborations on data provided by OES VdA, 2022
(Indicator VI.5)

Figure 43. Map of the total number of beds in the accommodations. Source: elaborations on data provided by OES VdA, 2022 (Indicator VI.6)

The profile of tourist attractiveness is an important aspect considered in the analysis of the region. Valle d'Aosta's alpine environment, with its natural beauty and cultural attractions, plays a significant role in attracting visitors and contributing to the vitality of the local tourism sector. The region's unique alpine landscape serves as a major tourist attraction. Its picturesque mountains, valleys, and scenic beauty captivate tourists seeking outdoor activities, such as hiking, mountaineering, and nature exploration. Additionally, Valle d'Aosta boasts a rich cultural and historical heritage, featuring medieval castles, forts, and archaeological sites. These sites showcase the region's ancient history and architectural wonders, attracting tourists interested in immersing themselves in the cultural richness of the territory. Valle d'Aosta offers a diverse range of tourist experiences, catering to different types of visitors. During the winter season, the region's renowned ski resorts, including Cervinia, La Thuile, and Pila, draw winter sports enthusiasts who seek optimal skiing conditions. The presence of these ski resorts contributes to the region's popularity as a winter tourism destination. In terms of hospitality, Valle d'Aosta provides a wide range of accommodation options to cater to the needs of tourists. These include hotels, alpine refuges, farmhouses, and other types of lodging, ensuring that visitors have suitable choices for their stay. The analysis of the region's tourist attractiveness considers the various factors that contribute to its appeal, including the natural landscape, cultural heritage, winter sports offerings, and the availability of accommodation facilities. Understanding the dynamics and impact of tourism in Valle d'Aosta is crucial for evaluating transportation needs, infrastructure development, and

overall regional planning. These facilities adapt to the needs of tourists, providing a quality service that contributes to the comfort and overall satisfaction of visitors. In quantitative terms, the data on tourist arrivals⁶ and presences⁷ were represented through four maps showing the number of tourists who visited the municipalities in total during the year 2022.

The analysis of tourism data in Valle d'Aosta has provided insights into the origin of tourists and their patterns of arrivals and stays. The data shows a balanced distribution between tourists coming from Italy and those coming from the rest of the world. The municipalities with the highest annual influx of tourists from Italy include Courmayeur, Aosta, Valtournenche, Ayas, and Saint Vincent, with arrival numbers ranging from 50,000 to 100,000. Following closely are municipalities such as Pré-Saint Didier, La Thuile, Cogne, and Gressoney Saint Jean, with arrivals ranging from 25,000 to 50,000. The situation is almost identical for foreign tourists, with a slight negative difference throughout the region.

One interesting observation is that when comparing arrivals and stays, the number of stays by foreign tourists is higher than that of national tourists. This suggests that foreign tourists tend to have longer stays on average. However, when considering the overall regional average values of the average length of stay, it is found that Italian tourists have longer stays (average of 2.60 days) compared to foreign tourists (average of 2.29 days). This indicates that Italian tourists tend to stay longer at the initial accommodation where they check-in during their holiday, or they move around less during their stay.

The constant influx of tourists to Valle d'Aosta can be attributed to the region's natural beauty and cultural heritage, which serve as major attractions. The analysis of tourism data is crucial for understanding the evolution of tourism in a mountainous environment and developing sustainable management strategies that maintain a balance between tourism development and the preservation of the local ecosystem.

By gaining insights into tourist behaviour, arrival patterns, and lengths of stay, policymakers and stakeholders can make informed decisions regarding infrastructure development, transportation, and the overall management of tourism in Valle d'Aosta.

Basic services to citizens

The quantification of users is the fundamental element for the choice of the sizing of a mobility model, but it is equally important to define the territorial basins in which this user is headed. To make up for the lack of specific data that tells us "from where" and "to" people move, it is necessary to attribute to the location of services a descriptive role of movement trends. In this regard, two types of social services par excellence have been identified, where users are among the greatest potential users of a mobility service that integrates the needs of individuals. We are talking about school services and health and social care services.

The map representation shows the percentage of the population that commutes for study purposes (represented by the colour of the municipalities) and the concentration of schools in the area (represented by punctual symbols with digits indicating the number of schools around the point).

⁶ The number of customers, both Italian and foreign, hosted in the accommodation establishments (hotel or complementary) during the period considered (number of customers who checked in at the accommodation establishments during the reference period).

⁷ The number of nights spent by customers in accommodation establishments (hotel or complementary).

Figure 44. Number of school buildings for each municipality. Source: own elaboration on data provided by ISTAT and Ministry of Education and Merit, 2023 (Indicator VII.1)

From the map, it is evident that most schools are located in the centres of the valley bottom, which are typically more densely populated and easily accessible areas. This concentration of schools in the valley bottom leaves some municipalities in the upper valley without easy access to this service. These upper valley municipalities, located far from the main connecting road infrastructures, are also clearly visible on the map, as schools are less prevalent in those areas. Another interesting observation is that municipalities with a higher supply of school facilities tend to have a lower percentage of school commuters. This suggests that when schools are more readily available in close proximity to the population, students have a shorter distance to travel, resulting in a lower percentage of commuters for study reasons.

The representation of school locations and commuting patterns provides insights into the areas that may lack educational services or have limited accessibility, particularly in the upper valley regions. This information can be valuable for planning and improving the provision of school facilities and developing integrated mobility services that cater to the needs of students in those areas. By understanding the spatial distribution of schools and commuting patterns, decision-makers can make informed decisions regarding the allocation of resources and the development of efficient and effective transportation solutions for students.

Below is the map that represents the number of students for each municipality. This is the number of children who study in that municipality and not the portion of the resident population that goes to school. The data was obtained through the sum of the students attending the institutes within each municipality. Here there is a clear correspondence with the data represented above of the location of the schools, in fact, the number is higher where the number of schools increases. From this map it is possible to identify macro basins of school demand that will then be taken into consideration for the definition of the areas of study.

Figure 45. Number of Students for each municipality. Source: elaboration on data provided by Department of Superintendence for Studies of the Valle d'Aosta region, 2023 (Indicator VII.2).

As anticipated at the beginning of this paragraph, the location of social-welfare and health-care facilities is the other category of services open to the public that is reported in this analysis of the territorial context. Also, in this case, as for schools, there is a clear polarization of these structures near the road infrastructures at the bottom of the valley. The map shows with numbered points the amount of structures aggregated by proximity location to allow an effective reading at this scale (as previously done for schools), and the number of beds in social and health facilities counted on a municipal scale. In this case the correspondence between beds and the number of structures is not always direct due to the fact that only the number of beds in the health ones are reported and also there could be municipalities in which there is a substantial presence of social welfare services but with the absence of social and health services.

To better specify what has just been said, a map has also been developed (Figure 45) in which the number of health facilities and the number of guests for each municipality is represented. The municipalities in which there are health services can be aggregated into three macro territorial areas that could be renamed "high", "medium" and "lower valley". The first aggregation ("Alta valle") consists of the municipalities of: La Thuile, Pré Saint Didier, and La Salle; the second ("Middle Valley") from the municipalities of: Doues, Roisan, Saint Christophe, Chervensod, Gressan, Cogne, Aymavilles, Fenis, Introd, Saint Pierre, Gignod and Aosta; while the third ("Lower valley") from the municipalities of: Verres, Valtournerche, Saint-Vincent, Pontey, Perloz, Montjovet, Hone, Gressoney-Saint-Jean, Gaby, Fontainemore, Donnas, Chatillon, Challand-Saint-Anselme, Brusson, Arnad, Antey-Saint-André. In almost all these municipalities, all the guests are almost always paid for by a single structure, except for the municipalities of Brusson, Chatillon, Pontey, Saint Christophe (with two structures), Gignod (with three structures) and Sarre (with four structures); over the capital of Aosta with 15 structures and 296 average annual guests.

Figure 46. Spatial distribution of Social-welfare facilities and number of beds in health-care structures for each municipality. Source: elaboration on data provided by Regional Statistical Observatory, 2020 (Indicators VII.3 and VII.5).

Figure 47. Number of guests in the social-health and number of health-care facilities aggregate for municipalities. Source: own elaboration on data provided by Regional Statistical Observatory, 2020 (Indicators VII.4 and VII.6).

Clustering analysis for the mobility generators, mobility demand and vulnerability in the Valle d'Aosta region

The summary and interpretative results of the three cluster analyses are presented below.

The algorithm that allowed the clustering to be created was implemented using R software, which returned the following output data, with some adjustments for better statistical representativeness and graphical rendering. Firstly, we find the dendrogram illustrating how the branches were cut from the initial generalisation into a single cluster.

The use of this analysis, however, allows us to have a characterisation of each cluster according to the most significant variable, either positively or negatively. This was then summarised in the table below.

Cluster analysis for the mobility generators

Cluster Dendrogram

Figure 48. Ascending Hierarchical Classification of the individuals. The classification made on individuals reveals 6 clusters.

*CLUSTER	MUNICIPALITIES	RELEVANCE OF VALUE variables are sorted from the strongest (High values) and weakest (Low values).
Cluster 1	Allein, Arvier, Avise, Bard, Bionaz, Brissogne, Challand-Saint-Victor, Chambave, Chamois, Champdepraz, Champorcher, Emarèse, Etroubles, Gressoney-La-Trinité, Issime, Issogne, Jovençon, La Magdeleine, Lillianes, Ollomont, Oyace, Rhêmes-Notre-Dame, Rhêmes-Saint-Georges, Saint-Denis, Saint-Marcel, Saint-Nicolas, Saint-Oyen, Saint-Rhémy-en-Bosses, Torgnon, Valgrisenche, Valpelline, Valsavarenche, Verrayes, Villeneuve	Low values for the variable: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Number of health-care facilities - Micro businesses - Capacity of health-care facilities, - number of social-welfare facilities - Employees - Capacity of social-welfare facilities, - small businesses, - Number of schools - Students - Medium and Big businesses
Cluster 2	Antey-Saint-André, Aymavilles, Challand-Saint-Anselme, Doues, Gaby, Fontainemore, Introd, La Salle,	High values for the variable: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Number of health-care facilities Low values for variables: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Medium and Big businesses

	Montjovet, Perloz, Pontey, Pré-Saint-Didier, Roisan	
Cluster 3	Arnad, Ayas, Charvensod, Cogne, Gressoney-Saint-Jean, Hône, La Thuile, Morgex, Nus, Pollein, Pont-Saint-Martin, Saint-Pierre	High values for the variables: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Medium and Big businesses - Micro businesses
Cluster 4	Brusson, Donnas, Gignod, Sarre	High values for the variables: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Capacity of health-care facilities - Capacity of social-welfare facilities - Number of health-care facilities - Number of social-welfare facilities
Cluster 5	Courmayeur, Pontboset, Quart, Saint-Christophe, Saint-Vincent, Valtournenche	High values for variables: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Small businesses - Employees - Micro businesses - Students - Medium and Big businesses - Number of schools - Number of social-welfare facilities
Cluster 6	Châtillon, Verrès	High values for variables: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Number of schools - Students - Medium and Big businesses - Employees - Capacity of social-welfare facilities - Number of social-welfare facilities - Micro businesses - Capacity of health-care facilities

Table 4. Summary of the relevant descriptive characters found within each cluster.

Figure 49. Cluster visualisation map for Mobility generators

Cluster analysis for the mobility demand

Figure 50. Ascending Hierarchical Classification of the individuals. The classification made on individuals reveals 6 clusters.

CLUSTER	MUNICIPALITIES	RELEVANCE OF VALUE *variables are sorted from the strongest (for high values) and weakest (for low values).
Cluster 1	Chamois, Champorcher, Fontainemore, Gaby, Gressoney-La-Trinité, La Magdeleine, Ollomont, Pontboset, Rhêmes-Notre-Dame, Saint-Rhémy-en-Bosses, Torgnon, Valgrisenche, Valsavarenche	Low values for the variables: Daily commuters for work Daily commuters for study population between 10 and 19 years population between 0 and 9 years population between 20 and 64 years Total population Population over 65 years
Cluster 2	Allein, Antey-Saint-André, Arvier, Avise, Bardt, Bionaz, Brissogne, Brusson, Challand-Saint-Anselme, Challand-Saint-Victor, Chambave, Champdepraz, Doues, Emarèse, Etroubles, Gressoney-Saint-Jean, Introd, Issime, Jovençan, La Thuile, Lillianes, Oyace, Perloz, Pontey, Pré-Saint-Didier, Rhêmes-Saint-Georges, Roisan, Saint-Denis, Saint-Nicolas, Saint-Oyen, Valpelline	High values for the variable: Daily commuters for work Low values for variables: Population over 65 years population between 20 and 64 years Population over 65 years population between 10 and 19 years population between 0 and 9 years
Cluster 3	Arnad, Ayas, Aymavilles, Cogne, Donnas, Fénis, Gignod, Hône, Issogne, La Salle, Montjivet, Morgex, Pollein, Saint-Marcel, Verrayes, Verrès, Villeneuve	variables whose values do not differ significantly from the mean.
Cluster 4	Courmayeur,	High values for the variables:

	Valtournenche	Tourist arrivals
Cluster 5	Charvensod	High values for variables: Tax of motorization
Cluster 6	Châtillon, Gressan, Nus, Pont-Saint-Martin, Quart, Saint-Christophe, Saint-Pierre, Saint-Vincent, Sarre	High values for variables: population between 0 and 9 years Total population population between 20 and 64 years population between 10 and 19 years population over 65 years

Table 5. Summary of the relevant descriptive characters found within each cluster.

Figure 51. Cluster visualisation map for Mobility demand

Cluster analysis for the vulnerability demand

Figure 52 : Ascending Hierarchical Classification of the individuals. The classification made on individuals reveals 6 clusters.

CLUSTER	MUNICIPALITIES	RELEVANCE OF VALUE *variables are sorted from the strongest (High values) and weakest (Low values).
Cluster 1	Brissogne, Champdepraz, Charvensod, Gignod, Gressan, Gressoney-La-Trinité, Jovençan, Montjovet, Nus, Pollein, Pontey, Quart, Roisan, Saint-Christophe, Saint-Denis, Saint-Marcel, Saint-Pierre, Sarre, Valtournenche, Villeneuve	High values for the variable: - Youthfulness index - Population trend (2011-2021) Low values for the variables: - Old age index (>65 years) - Old age index (>80 years)
Cluster 2	Arnad, Arvier, Ayas, Aymavilles, Bionaz, Brusson, Challand-Saint-Anselme, Courmayeur, Doues, Emarèse, Etroubles, Fénis, Fontainemore, Gressoney-Saint-Jean, Hône, Introd, La Magdeleine, La Salle, La Thuile, Lillianes, Morgex, Oyace, Perloz, Pré-Saint-Didier, Saint-Nicolas, Saint-Oyen, Torgnon, Valpelline, Verrayes	Low values for variable: - Population density
Cluster 3	Pont-Saint-Martin, Saint-Vincent, Verrès	High values for the variable: - Population density
Cluster 4	Chamois, Champorcher, Ollomont, Valgrisenche	High values for the variable: - Old Age index (>80 years) Low values for the variable: - Youthfulness index
Cluster 5	Allein, Antey-Saint-André, Avise, Bard, Challand-Saint-Victor, Chambave, Châtillon, Cogne, Donnas, Gaby, Issime, Issogne, Pontboset, Rhêmes-Saint-Georges, Saint-Rhémy-en-Bosses, Valsavarenche	High values for variables: - Old Age index (>80 years) - Old Age index (>65 years) Low values for variables: - Population trend (2011-2020) - Youthfulness index
Cluster 6	Rhêmes-Notre-Dame	Low values for variables: - Population trend (2011-2020) - Youthfulness index

Table 6. Summary of the relevant descriptive characters found within each cluster.

Figure 53. Cluster visualisation map for Vulnerability demand

Suitable schemes of intervention of digital technologies for health

There are several suitable schemes for the intervention of digital technologies in healthcare. These schemes aim to improve patient care, enhance efficiency, and facilitate communication and collaboration among healthcare professionals. A non-exhaustive list of examples drawn from the literature includes:

- **Electronic Health Records (EHR):** Implementing EHR systems allows healthcare providers to store and access patient medical records electronically. EHRs enable seamless sharing of information between different healthcare facilities, reducing errors and improving patient safety. They also facilitate data analysis for research and population health management.
- **Telemedicine:** Telemedicine involves the use of digital communication technologies to provide remote healthcare services. It allows patients to consult with healthcare professionals through video conferencing, phone calls, or messaging platforms. Telemedicine is particularly useful for patients in rural or remote areas, individuals with limited mobility, and for follow-up appointments and chronic disease management.
- **Mobile Health (mHealth) Applications:** mHealth apps can be used on smartphones and other mobile devices to support various aspects of healthcare. These apps can provide personalized health information, reminders for medication and appointments, fitness tracking, and access to telemedicine services. They empower patients to actively participate in their own healthcare management.
- **Health Information Exchange (HIE):** HIE systems enable the secure sharing of patient health information between healthcare organizations. They promote interoperability and seamless transfer of data, allowing healthcare providers to access a patient's complete medical history and make more informed decisions. HIEs improve care coordination, reduce duplicate tests, and enhance patient outcomes.
- **Remote Patient Monitoring (RPM):** RPM involves the use of digital devices to monitor patients' health status remotely. These devices, often associated to telemedicine praxes, can collect and transmit data such as vital signs, glucose levels, or activity levels to healthcare providers. RPM allows for early detection of health issues, enables proactive interventions, and reduces the need for hospital visits.
- **Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML):** AI and ML algorithms can analyze large volumes of medical data to identify patterns, predict outcomes, and support clinical decision-making. They can assist in diagnosing diseases, recommending treatment plans, and identifying potential risks. AI-powered chatbots and virtual assistants can also provide 24/7 patient support and answer common health-related questions.
- **Wearable Devices:** Wearable devices, such as smartwatches and fitness trackers, can monitor various health parameters, including heart rate, sleep patterns, and physical activity. These devices promote self-monitoring and can help individuals make healthier lifestyle choices. They can also alert healthcare professionals in case of abnormal readings or emergencies.

It's important to note that the implementation of digital technologies in healthcare should prioritize patient privacy and data security (Zarour et al., 2021). Additionally, healthcare providers should ensure proper training and education for both patients and staff to maximize the benefits of these interventions (WHO, 2009). If not addressed correctly, these two issues could negatively impact the economic viability and social acceptability of digital solutions for healthcare (Scott Kruse et al., 2018). In the following paragraph, we propose several key-points to be included in the ex-ante assessment of the potential implementation of a particular kind of tool of digital solution in the healthcare system: telemedicine.

Telemedicine: definition and applications

Telemedicine refers to the provision of healthcare services, diagnosis, treatment, and monitoring of patients remotely using telecommunication technologies (Haleem et al., 2021). It enables healthcare professionals to interact with patients virtually, eliminating the need for in-person visits. The main practices associated to telemedicine are (Jafarzadeh et al., 2022): (i) video consultations, where doctors and patients communicate in real-time through video conferencing platforms and the doctor can diagnose, provide medical advice, and prescribe medications remotely; (ii) remote monitoring, meaning that patients can use wearable devices or home monitoring equipment to track vital signs, such as blood pressure, heart rate, or glucose levels. The data is transmitted to healthcare professionals who can remotely monitor the patient's condition and provide necessary interventions; (iii) online patient portals, used by patients to securely access their medical records, test results, and communicate with healthcare providers through secure online platforms; (iv) telepsychiatry and other mental health services delivered through telemedicine, allowing patients to receive counseling, therapy, or psychiatric evaluations remotely; (v) systems to store-and-forward medical images, such as X-rays or MRIs, to be securely transmitted to specialists for remote review and consultation; (vi) remote surgical assistance, entailing that surgeons can provide guidance and expertise to remote locations during surgical procedures using real-time video communication. These six types of application illustrate the diverse applications of telemedicine, highlighting its potential to enhance healthcare delivery, increase accessibility, and improve patient outcomes.

Telemedicine in remote areas: costs and benefits

Telemedicine has been a valuable tool for delivering healthcare services in remote areas. However, the academic literature has also shown that advantages might be offset by disadvantages under certain circumstances. Table 2 summarizes the main advantages and the main risks related to the implementation of telemedicine (Hwei and Octavius, 2021) in remote areas.

Advantages
<p>Increased access to healthcare: Telemedicine eliminates geographical barriers, allowing people in remote areas to access healthcare services that may not be readily available locally. It enables patients to consult with healthcare providers, specialists, and even receive second opinions without traveling long distances.</p> <p>Improved healthcare outcomes: By facilitating early intervention and timely access to medical advice, telemedicine can help prevent or manage chronic conditions (Lia et al., 2022). Patients in remote areas can receive timely diagnoses, follow-up care, and appropriate treatment plans, leading to better health outcomes.</p>
<p>Cost-effective: Telemedicine can reduce healthcare costs for patients in remote areas. By eliminating travel expenses, time off work, and accommodation costs associated with in-person visits, patients can save money. Additionally, telemedicine can help avoid unnecessary emergency room visits or hospitalizations by managing conditions remotely.</p>
<p>Time-saving: Telemedicine saves time for both patients and healthcare providers. Patients can connect with healthcare professionals without having to spend hours traveling to a clinic or hospital. Similarly, healthcare providers can attend to more patients remotely, leading to increased efficiency in their practice.</p>
<p>Specialist consultations: In remote areas, access to specialists can be limited. Telemedicine bridges this gap by enabling remote consultations with specialists. Local healthcare providers can collaborate with specialists through video conferencing, ensuring patients receive expert advice and recommendations without the need for travel.</p>
Risks
<p>Limited physical examination: Telemedicine relies on audio and video communication, which may not provide the same level of physical examination as an in-person visit. Healthcare providers may face challenges in assessing certain physical signs, such as palpation or auscultation, potentially affecting diagnostic accuracy.</p>
<p>Technological barriers: Access to stable internet connectivity and appropriate technology devices can be a challenge in remote areas. The reliability and availability of internet connections can impact the quality of video calls, leading to communication issues or disrupted consultations.</p>
<p>Lack of personal connection: Some patients may prefer face-to-face interactions with their healthcare providers. Telemedicine can lack the personal touch and bedside manner that patients may value in traditional healthcare settings. Building rapport and trust solely through telecommunication can be more challenging. Integrating evaluation scores to match physicians' assessments and patients' perception might reduce this type of risks (Mangia et al., 2022).</p>

Privacy and security concerns: Transmitting sensitive health information through telemedicine platforms may raise privacy and security concerns. Remote consultations must adhere to strict privacy regulations and ensure secure data transmission and storage to protect patient confidentiality.

Limited scope of care: While telemedicine is effective for many types of consultations and follow-up care, certain healthcare procedures and examinations require in-person visits. Surgical procedures, radiological investigations, or complex interventions may not be possible through telemedicine alone, necessitating travel to a healthcare facility.

Table 7. Telemedicine in remote areas: advantages and risks

Overall, telemedicine offers significant advantages for healthcare delivery in remote areas, such as improved access and timesaving. However, challenges related to physical examination, technology, personal connection, and scope of care should be carefully considered to ensure its successful implementation and patient satisfaction. In addition, although telemedicine can have cost-effective outcomes for patients, the academic literature has shown that its deployment in remote areas can be relatively expensive in terms of investment in equipment and infrastructure, an issue that is particularly relevant in contexts where insurance schemes do not cover telemedicine applications (Jafarzadeh et al., 2022).

Performing a cost-benefit analysis of telemedicine involves evaluating both the financial and non-financial impacts of implementing and utilizing telemedicine services. For what pertains the benefits, the literature discusses three main groups of advantages: cost savings, increased revenue, and patient outcomes:

- **Cost savings** include reduced hospital visits (by reducing unnecessary hospital visits, especially for follow-up appointments, resulting in cost savings related to transportation, parking, and missed workdays); lower infrastructure costs by eliminating the need for physical infrastructure expansion, such as building new clinics or hospitals, potentially reducing capital expenditures; reduced readmissions, thanks to remote patient monitoring and virtual consultations that can lead to better management of chronic conditions, reducing the likelihood of hospital readmissions and associated costs.
- **Increased Revenue** includes an expanded reach (telemedicine enables healthcare providers to reach patients in remote or underserved areas, expanding their patient base and potentially increasing revenue); time efficiency that might result in increasing patient throughput by reducing wait times, allowing providers to see more patients in a given time frame and potentially generating more revenue.
- **Improved patient outcomes** through enhanced access to care (telemedicine provides convenient access to healthcare services, particularly for individuals with limited mobility, those in rural areas, or those with transportation challenges); better medication adherence because remote monitoring and virtual consultations can improve medication adherence, leading to better patient outcomes and potentially reducing healthcare costs associated with complications; early Intervention through timely virtual consultations and remote monitoring that can facilitate early intervention and preventive care, potentially reducing the severity of illnesses and their associated costs.

The main costs associated to the deployment of telemedicine programs turn around three main issues:

- **Initial Investment:** Telemedicine implementation requires an upfront investment in technology infrastructure, software platforms, and staff training.
- **Reimbursement and Regulations:** Understanding reimbursement policies and ensuring compliance with regulatory requirements is crucial for successful telemedicine implementation.
- **Technical Support:** Ongoing technical support for telemedicine platforms and troubleshooting issues may be required, incurring additional costs.

It's important to note that the cost-benefit analysis of telemedicine may vary depending on the healthcare setting, patient population, and specific telemedicine program. A study examining the cost-effectiveness of telemedicine solutions implemented in remote areas in Greece, for

instance, showed evidence of substantial economic and social savings (Kouskoukis and Botsaris, 2017), whereas a systematic review of the economic evaluation of telemedicine in Japan showed mixed results, with positive that were found for teledermatology and teleradiology, and inconclusive results for telehomecare (Akiyama and Yoo, 2016). In reviewing the literature on the subject, Farabi et al. (2020) found evidence of cost-effectiveness in the implementation of telemedicine protocols for patients with cardiovascular diseases, while Lee et al. (2018) found evidence of cost-effectiveness by reviewing economic evaluations of telemedicine applications to patients with diabetes. However, according to the results of a literature review conducted by Eze et al. (2020), telemedicine in OECD countries produced cost-effective outcomes only in 7 assessments (39%) out of 18. Moreover, the authors stress the relevance of an efficiency-equity trade-off resulting in unequal access to telemedicine for those households living in marginalized rural areas, who are more often sicker and less used to adopt digital innovations than urban users. Conducting a thorough analysis that considers the local context, projected utilization, and potential outcomes is therefore the best way to estimate the financial and non-financial implications of telemedicine implementation.

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